

THE LIFE AND WORK OF ABDULLA AVLONI

J. SH. Mustafayev

U.F. Jozilov

Samarkand branch of Tashkent University of Information Technologies.

Samarkand, Uzbekistan

E-mail: umarjonjozilov@gmail.com

Abstract: In this article, the countries where Abdullah Avloni sought knowledge during his life and work, the spiritual heritage of his works, and the information that has reached us are described in this article.

Key words: jurisprudence, hadith scholar, madrasa, teacher, dictionary, faith, theater, press, astronomy.

The famous enlightener, talented poet and pedagogue Abdulla Avloni was born on July 12, 1878 in Tashkent in a peasant family and was educated in an old school. He wrote about it in his biography: "I started studying at the madrasa in Okhchi neighborhood from the age of 12. From the age of 13, I worked as a laborer in the summer, helped my family, and studied in the winter. From the age of 14, I started writing various poems according to that time. During these times, I read the newspaper "Tarjumon" and became aware of the times. Avloni graduated from madrasa and worked as a school teacher. He reformed the teaching and learning method, established a new type of school and carried out important educational activities such as imparting modern knowledge to young pedagogues-students, teaching Eastern and Western languages. Abdulla Avloni wrote such textbooks as "The First Teacher", "The Second Teacher" (1912), "Tarikh", "Turkish Gulistan or Ethics" (1913), which were a phenomenon for the time. Avloni, who began his creative career in 1895, created poems, short stories, feuilletons and short dramatic works under the pseudonyms "Kabin", "Shuhrat", "Hijran", "Avloni", "Suraya", "Abulfayz", "Indamas". In his works, the poet criticizes the backwardness and ignorance of his time and calls people to knowledge and enlightenment. Before 1917, Abdulla Avloni, who grew up among the local people

as a publisher and journalist, founded such newspapers as "Shuhrat" and "Asiyo" in Tashkent. He wrote dramatic works such as "Is Advocacy Easy?", "Ikki Muhabbat", "Wedding", "Sezd", "Layli and Majnun", "The Dead", and in them the tragic consequences of ignorance, heresy and ignorance. , exposes rude and naughty customs. As a poet, Abdulla Avloni wrote many poems. Whether his poems are directed against old customs, or about love or education, all of them sing about man, his moral beauty and spiritual wealth. For example, in the poem "In our country", he condemns the greedy people who spend a lot of money and wealth for life, but do not see the yellow chaka for the upbringing of children, saying that "they do not pay attention to money for science". Especially his book "Literature" (1915) stands out in this respect. In 1913, Avloni founded the "Turon" theater troupe, and along with creating original stage works for this theater, he also translated the plays of his fellow playwrights into Uzbek. In the 20s, Abdulla Avloni not only participated in the development of the education and culture of the Uzbek people, but also played a certain role in the social and political life of the neighboring Afghan people. For some time, he served as the Minister of Public Education of Afghanistan, and then as the consul-ambassador of the Union of Soviets in Afghanistan. Avloni joined the Jadidist movement at the beginning of the 20th century. He became known as one of the active participants of the jadids in Tashkent. From 1906, he began to participate in the press with his poems. He studied Arabic, Persian, and Russian languages, read the works of thinkers who created in these languages, and translated some of them (for example, the works of Leo Tolstoy, Konstantin Ushinsky) into Uzbek. In 1906. In 1907, "Taraqqi" published "Shuhrat" newspapers at his home. After these newspapers were closed, in 1908 he secretly published the newspaper "Asiyo". After issue 6, the government also banned this newspaper. Avloni was the first to offer to teach chemistry, geography, physics and astronomy at school. He tried to spread advanced ideas to the people through the school: he opened a new method school for local children in the Mirobod quarter of Tashkent city (1908), he himself taught native language and literature. In 1909, he founded "Jamiyati Khairiya" and

educated orphans. In the same year, he published the first volume of his four-part poetry collection entitled "Literature or National Poems". In 1912, Avloni opened a two-class school in Degrez neighborhood of Tashkent.

Avloni wrote and published manuals and reading books for new schools (for example, "The First Teacher", 1911; "The Second Teacher", 1912; "Turkish Gulistan Yakhud Akhlaq", 1913; "Literature or National Poems" in 4 volumes). collection, 1909-1915; "School Gulistan", 1915; "Workers' riot", 1917, etc.). Together with such progressives as Munavvarqori, Muhammadjon Podshokhojayev, Tavallo, Rustambek Yusufbekov, Nizomiddin Khojayev, Shokirjon Rahimi, he founded the companies "Publishing" (1914), "School" (1916). Avloni also used the art of theater to raise public awareness. In 1913, he founded the "Turkistan" theater troupe and took an active part in its work. In 1910-1916, he translated and staged a number of plays. Avloni's stage works were staged in cities such as Tashkent, Fergana, Andijan, Kokan, Khojand. In these works, the broad scenes of Turkestan life at the beginning of the 20th century are expressed. Mannon Uighur was educated in Avloni's troupe; Hamza, Azerbaijani playwrights Uzayr Hajibekov, Ruhullo collaborated with the troupe. After the October Revolution, the lack of freedom promised to the people led to depression in the poet's work (the poem "In the sad hour", 1919). "Is Advocacy Easy" (1914), "Pinac" (1916), "Us and You" (1917), "Portuguese Revolution", "Two Loves", "The Storm", "Fox and Crow", "Workers' Song" ", "Motherland" (1916), "School", "Kindergarten", "From the language of a lazy student", "A landscape from the mountains", "Address to the nation", "Tortuq to the workers", "Koklam keldi", "Sound", etc. Articles such as "Purpose and purpose" (April 9, 1908), "About our situation" (February 14, 1908), the allegorical story "The Scourge of Jealousy" and others.

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